

Contemporary Reality and Siddheswar Chattopadhyay: A Modern Sanskrit Dramatist

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Abstract: The oldest language among the Indian languages is Sanskrit. Some ignorant people try to dismiss it as a dead language. But even in the present day, Sanskrit is a very rich and ever-flowing language that has maintained its existence in the wilderness. Many scholars continue to enrich this language through their creative literatures. There has also been innovation in the field of Sanskrit literature of the 20th and 21st centuries. Along with the Vedas, Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata, Purāṇas, etc., contemporary social, political and economic issues have also taken their place there in it. As a result, Modern Sanskrit Literature has largely become timeless. Contribution of Siddheswar Chattopadhyay (Burodā), a modern Sanskrit dramatist from West Bengal is the subject of the present article.

Keywords: Sanskrit Literature, Vedas, Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata, Purāṇas, Modern Sanskrit Drama, Siddheswar Chattopadhyay, Timeless reality.

Introduction: Literature is an expression of a society. Like literature in other languages written in the twentieth and twenty first century, Sanskrit Literature occupied an important place in contemporary society. The horrors of World War II, terrorism, corruption of leaders and ministers, naxal movement, chaotic student politics, electoral corruption, black money problem, women's oppression, child marriage, dowry system etc., were the subject of Sanskrit literature. Several Sanskrit dramas were written on the socio-economic, political, religious and educational issues of the time. The tradition of portraying contemporary issues through the drama is very old in Sanskrit literature. Bharata, in his *Nāṭyaśāstra* portrayed the dark side of the life of the elite community of that time and the sages were very angry about it. Even in recent times, it is seen that dramas that go against the rulers or the elite society are stopped.

Judging by the style of the modern Sanskrit plays, it can be seen that in addition to the *Nāndi*, *Prastāvanā*, *Bharatavākya* of the ancient drama tradition, the influence of the illusion theory of the modern tradition, Brecht, Beckett and the Third Theater of Badal Sarkar are there in. Again, it has been seen in many plays that the rhetorical signs of Sanskrit drama that are in accordance with the scriptures and theories have been broken. However, this did not interrupt the audience's enjoyment. These plays reflected the social consciousness of the time, political thoughts, domestic and international problems, educational awareness, satire on superstition, protest against the injustice of human nature and psychology. These dramatists protested against social and political injustice in special way in a satirical manner or in the form of farce (*prahasana*), basically a combination of Satire, Irony, Wit and Humour.¹ Many contemporary dramatists have written such dramas in Sanskrit based on contemporary reality. In the present article, we will discuss about Siddheswar Chattopadhyay (Burodā), one of such dramatists from West Bengal.

Siddheswar Chattopadhyay (Buroda): Professor Siddheshwar Chattopadh-

yay, the pioneer of a new genre of modern Sanskrit drama in West Bengal, is better known as Buroda. He was not only a dramatist, but also a theatre director and a prominent dramaturgist. He was the first person to present Brecht on the stage of Bengal as well as India through Sanskrit drama. Not only that, but perhaps he is also credited with bringing Brecht to the stage for the first time in South Asia. That is why his name is written in gold letters in the Brecht Gallery in Berlin. He directed the play Galilee, translated by Ritwik Ghatak, and also acted in the role of Cardinal. Director Siddheshwar received the 'Golden Pitcher' Award for his contribution to the theatre world.

Siddheshwar was born on 27 February 1918 in Jessore district of present-day Bangladesh. He studied at the University of Calcutta. He worked as the Head of the Department of Sanskrit at Burdwan University for a long time. He also worked in the Research Department of Sanskrit College. He also held the post of secretary of the Sanskrit Sahitya Parishat of Kolkata. He wrote four dramas based on contemporary socio-political aspect. They are *Dharitrīpatinirvācana*², *Atha kim*³, *Nanāvitaḍita*⁴ and *Svargīyahāsana*⁵. All four dramas are written in a new style. Needless to say, Brecht's outstanding influence is evident in each of them.

Dharitrīpatinirvācana: *Dharitrīpatinirvācana* is a unique satire based on international political issues. The drama satirizes the attempts of powerful countries to exert power and influence over weaker countries, focusing on the election of the president of the UNO. It shows with sharp satire how strong countries, through their lust for dominance and deadly weapons, push weaker countries towards destruction. The UNO was established in 1945 to maintain world peace and security and to promote mutual friendship and goodwill among different countries. But in many cases, the UNO has not been able to find lasting peace or solutions. This drama points the finger at that inability.

The setting of the drama is a bar, owned by God himself. God's assistant is Viśvakarmā. God has a marriageable daughter, whose name is Dharitrī. Dharitrī is extraordinarily beautiful, so there are a lot of suitors around her. Just as flies fly around when there are jars of gaggery. None of them love Dharitrī, none of them want her well-being, and they only want to take possession of her. So some try to take possession of her by the power of money, some by force of man-power and some by force of both money and power. And those who have no money or power also indulge in the power of so-called well-wishing brothers or uncles. But no one gets Dharitrī. No one is taken into their hearts. They themselves fight, kick, shoot, and everyone returns home injured and devastated. Not once or twice, but every time Dharitrī's husband selection meeting is held, the same outcome occurs. It never ends well, not even to this day. The dramatist says— “रचनाकालात् परम् अतीतानि कति वर्षाणि, किं चित् परिवर्तनं न जातं नाटिकावर्णितस्य दृश्यस्यैवा। अङ्कस्तु नाधुनापि परिसमाप्तः। धरित्रीपतिनिर्वाचनसभाया आयोजनं प्रचलिततरां, सभा तु नानुष्ठिताद्यापि।”⁶

This drama was written in 1967 and was staged that same year by the artists of the Sanskrit Sahitya Parishat under the direction of the dramatist himself. It was published by the Sanskrit Sahitya Parishat in 1971.

Aatha Kim: In 1969, Siddheshwar Chattopadhyay wrote a satirical drama, named *Aatha Kim*. The play was performed at the 55 annual function of the Sanskrit Sahitya Parishat in 1972. Later, the drama was published by the Sanskrit Sa-

hitya Parishat in 1974. Through this drama, the dramatist has made a sharp and straightforward satire on the electoral system of a so-called democratic country like India. Siddheshwar's *Aatha Kim* belongs to the stage of *Absurd Drama* written in Bengali following the German, French, and American neo-drama movements. The influence of this strange taste is visible everywhere in the drama, starting from *Nāndī* to the the *Bharata vakya*. In *Nāndī*, he has praised a new god called *Samudbhata*— 'समुद्रटाख्यं नव नाट्यदेवम्'. Another notable thing is that the dramatist has not given any specific names to the Character. He has represented the male characters with consonants like *ka, kha, ga, gha* etc. and the female characters with vowels like *ā, ū* etc. It seems that without naming the characters specifically, the dramatist has meant that here no individual is the main character, but the group is the main character. His characters like *ka, kha, ga, gha* etc. are like symbols of different classes of society. In this case, one can feel the shadow of Samuel Beckett's '*Writing for Godot*'. Even despite the influence of Badal Sarkar's *Evṃ Indrajit*, the dramatist has shown the uniqueness of vowels and consonants in naming the characters.

Although the harsh reality of India's political scene— anarchy, lust for power, strikes, blockades, electoral corruption, false promises, the general public's aversion to the vulgar speeches of leaders, and the public's lack of trust in all political parties is depicted here, but it does not become a poster drama.

A common man, annoyed by the leader's speech, can be heard saying— is this a history class or not? Are we all your students? गः— किमेषा विद्यालयस्य इतिहासश्रेणी? वयं किं छात्राः? Another person says— this time I will put a stamp next to the names of all the candidates in the election (that is, I will spoil the vote)— गः— वारे तु अस्मिन् सर्वेषामेव नाम्नां पार्श्वे चिह्नान्यङ्कयिष्यामि.⁸ Even then, the Honourable Supreme Court had not introduced NOTA. Here, the play has opened the way to the truth in the words of Aristotle. Sometimes, the common people have severely ridiculed the inhumanity of the leaders— hey, there are young people to be martyred. They want to be martyrs, but if you call a meeting under the pillar that has their name on it, many will be called martyrs. The text says—

“ङः— तदर्थं तु वर्तन्ते तरुणाः।

आः— ये तावत् शहीदाख्यमुपाधिं लब्धुकामाः।

कः— तत्र तु तन्नामधेयः स्तम्भो वर्तते, तत्र यदि सभा काचिदनुष्ठीयते तर्हि बहवः शहीदेत्याख्यभाजो भवेयुः।”⁹

And in *Bharatavākya*, the dramatist has highlighted the eternal truth of politics (looking at the pace of time, now I want to be good, only mine or not yours)—

“कालस्य गतिमालोक्य सांप्रतं प्रार्थयामहे

अस्तु मे मङ्गलं नित्यं भवतामस्तु वा न वा।”¹⁰

Svargīyahāsana: Inspired by Rabindranath Tagore's *Svargīya Prahāsana*, Siddheshwar Chattopadhyay wrote *Svargīyahāsana* in 1974. In it, the dramatist sharply criticized the various weaknesses of MPs and ministers. The drama depicts the immoral activities of political leaders, such as hypocrisy, corruption, greed, intrigue, etc. Throughout the drama, the dramatist wants to show that such corruption, heartlessness, bribery, etc. are common in all times, countries, and people of all religions. Just as the tapping of telephones, spying on others, etc. are mentioned, the meaninglessness of the parliamentary working methods and the feather-brained government system is revealed in this drama.

It has been said before that this drama is of all ages, all times and all religions. Therefore, the dramatist has not placed any time limit on the naming of the characters. Here the characters are— gods of heaven like Bṛhaspati, Indra, etc. an emperor of the ancient era like Aśoka, an emperor of the medieval era like Akbar. He has shown how everyone is conspiring together. He has also shown the naked reality of greed for power, corruption, there is no difference between that era and the present. Through the dialogue of Bṛhaspati, he has said— “I do not know whether the party is for my own interests, the country is for the interests of the party, or the country is for the interests of the country— स्वार्थरक्षायै स्वार्थसिद्धये वा संघः, संघस्वार्थाय च देशः, देशाय तावत् किं तन्नाहं जाने।”¹¹ And our leaders say, first the country, then the party, then me. But the funny thing is they do not follow any order. Everywhere it is me, me and me.

The dramatist has shown politics in every field, from educational institutions to tea shops. Politics in the name of communal harmony, politics of division, money, alcohol, girls, whatever one likes to be brought into the party; and if someone does not come to that, then the politics of making false cases or getting them involved in trouble and getting them into the party for some reason, has been shown it all. He has also shown how actors, even though they have no connection with politics, are getting ministers or MPs elected. He has shown how motion of no-confidence is being brought in the cabinet. Some are again wavering. However, everyone has the same goal that their party should get the responsibility of an office that has a system for embezzling a lot of money.

However, he not only pointed out the problems, but also provided solutions to the problems at times. Although it is never became a slogan. He repeatedly said that the common people should be given due respect. If necessary, the leader should be strict. Deceit should be defeated with deception. Leaders should come down among the common people. The drama ended with the declaration of the victory of communism— let the gap between rich and poor be bridged, may the leader who works for the welfare of the people win—

“जयतु जयतु देवराजो जयतु जनकल्याणकारी।

(येन) ध्वस्तो भेदः स्वर्गनरकयोर्लब्धा सहायता धुन्ध-पुङ्गवोः,

स जयतु संकटोत्तीर्णो वज्रपाशधारी

जयतु जयतु देवराजो जयतु जनकल्याणकारी।”¹²

Nanavitāḍita: Siddheshwar Chattopadhyay wrote *Nanavitāḍita* to prove the futility of the government policy of declaring Sanskrit language dead and removing it from the curriculum despite its survival under the dominance of English and other regional languages and the wrong policies of the government. In this drama, he pointed out the hypocrisy, stupidity, and confusion of the leading figures in the field of education. The drama was published in the journal of Sanskrit Sahitya Parishat in 1974. The style of the drama is completely new in Sanskrit drama. There is no *Nāndī* in the drama. The first attempt to build a bridge between the actors and the audience is seen in this drama, as seen in Badal Sarkar's *Third Theatre*.

The word Nanā means mother. Here, mother is the Sanskrit language. The destruction of that Sanskrit mother is *Nanavitāḍita*. The drama has a very simple style of sharp satire aimed at the so-called educationists of West Bengal. The dramatist wants to show how the people of Sanskrit are destroying Sanskrit. How three experts of Sanskrit strategically confirmed the destruction of Sanskrit. Three

experts have been called to examine the dying Nanā. Some of them are for Hindi, some for English and some for Bengali. They examine and declare Nanā dead. Then one of them, Basukumbha, said that if the body is carefully kept in a museum, it will bring joy to many in the future. Another, Svakumbha, said that not only that, but it will also be useful for research. Another Sanskrit scholar said that a research institute must be established to preserve Nanā's memory. Then Nanā's daughter, Uttarā, said that arrangements should be made to get a grant from the government—

“पूरवी— किन्तु ननादेवी तु अधुनापि संज्ञां न लब्धवती। किं विधेयम्?

उत्तरा (स्वगतम्)— चिरमेव लुप्तसंज्ञा यथा स्यात्तदेव विधास्यते।

वसुकुम्भः— प्रत्नशालायां सुरक्षितो ननादेहः कौतुकाय भविष्यति बहूनामगामिनि काले।

स्वकुम्भः— गवेषणाकार्यस्यापि सहायता भविष्यति।

पण्डितः— नना-स्मृतिरक्षायै मठस्थापनमवश्यमेव करणीयम्। नना-स्मृतिरक्षायै गवेषणागारः कश्चित् प्रतिष्ठापयितव्यः।

उत्तरा— सर्वकारसकाशात् तदर्थमनुदानं यथाचिरेणैव कालेन आयाति तदर्थमहं यतिष्ये।”¹³

This heartlessness of the scholars is revealed throughout the entire drama. By composing such a drama in Sanskrit, Siddheshwar wanted to prove that Sanskrit never dies. No one can kill a language. It survives on its own excellence, much like a river.

Although background music is mentioned in Bharata's Natyashastra, its use is not seen much in Sanskrit dramas, as much as it is seen in this play by Siddheshwar. His use of music is also impeccable—

“शृणु शृणु समागत सर्वगुणिजन

अधिकारिगीतेऽधुना दीयतां हि मनः।

ननावृत्तं समालम्ब्य निवेदते मया

सरसकटुकाकथा हीनताललया।”¹⁴

The tunes of *Pāñchālī* have become folkloric in *Mukharā*. Verbal art has made the farce more lively, heart-warming and popular—

“अस्ति तत्र ननानाम्नी देवी महीयसी

सर्वजनवन्द्या सा हि माता गरीयसी।

पूरवी कन्यका तस्या रङ्गदेशे जाता

उत्तरापि सुता तस्यास्तत्र समागता।।

काले तत्र समागता विदेशिनी कन्या।

रूपयौवनवती सा सर्वजनमान्या।।”¹⁵

Conclusion:

Siddheshwar witnessed the anarchy and corruption of post-independence India from very close quarters. His heart was repeatedly wounded by that pain. These plays are an expression of that very anguish. The novelty in the prologues and epilogues of the plays is quite striking. Following Brecht, he sometimes raised questions in the minds of the audience and at other times tried to suggest solutions. Through his unique application of techniques, he created a new concept of drama in the world of Sanskrit theatre. Through each of his plays, he repeatedly protested against injustice. In every play, he presented the harsh truth and brutal reality to the audience. He offered sharp satire against the injustices of society and those who perpetrate them. In each of his plays, the blend of tradition and modernity is striking. The light of that modernity has not faded even today. This is where the timeless relevance of these plays lies.

Endnotes

1. Rita Chattopadhyay, *Adhunik Sanskrita Sahitya: 1910-2010 Traditional and Modernism*, p. 7.
2. *Organ of Sanskrit Sahitya parishat*. Kolkata, 1971.
3. *Ibid.* 1972
4. *Ibid.* 1974
5. *Ibid.* 1977
6. Rita Chattopadhyay, *Adhunik Sanskrita Sahitya: 1910-2010 Traditional and Modernism*, p. 128.
7. Siddheswar Chattopadhyay. *Atha Kim*. p. 20.
8. *Ibid.*
9. *Ibid.*
10. *Ibid.* p. 24.
11. *Organ of Sanskrit Sahitya parishat*. Kolkata, 1977. p. 4.
12. *Ibid.*
13. *Organ of Sanskrit Sahitya parishat*. Kolkata, 1974. pp.22-24.
14. *Ibid.* p. 24.
15. *Ibid.*

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